

Network Analysis (Project Report)

Abstract

In the context of quantitative literary analysis studies, this research aims to verify the existence of a predictive model of characters' death in literary works. Using George R. R. Martin's book of *A Game of Thrones* as a model, the weighted degree, eigenvector centrality, betweenness centrality and local clustering coefficient for each node were calculated. After that, a monadic level test of logistic regression took place between these measures and the life and death condition of the characters at the end of the book. The outcome of the test did not lead to rejecting the null hypothesis, since no statistically significant relationship was found, but it did result in interesting reflections on the work and poetics of George R. R. Martin, whose search for realism prompts the author to intentionally decree the death of his characters regardless of their centrality.

Context

The general context of this work is literary studies, that is the study, evaluation, and interpretation of literature. In particular, it is a study of quantitative literary analysis, a branch of research which includes studies that “represent elements or characteristics of literary texts numerically, applying the powerful, accurate, and widely accepted methods of mathematics to measurement, classification, and analysis” (Hoover, 2013). Modern quantitative studies of literature began in the second half of the nineteenth century, but it was in the 1980s that the most intense and rich in results activity took place. The reason is to be found in the progressive diffusion of electronic texts, of dedicated statistical techniques and, above all, of powerful computers that have made it possible to obtain much more precise and persuasive results. In this way, it was possible to borrow methods and tools from disciplines such as statistics, computer science or network analysis to carry out previously impossible literary studies. Among the various applications of quantitative literary studies, there is precisely the study of the interactions between the characters of a literary work through network analysis and it is on this aspect that the present research will focus.

Problem and Motivation

The aim of this work is to find a model capable of predicting the death of the characters in any literary work, depending on their centrality in the network. The hypothesis is that it is possible to predict how likely a character could die based on how many other characters rely on that node to interact with each other. To avoid structural holes, the author will be less inclined to kill characters who, once dead, would prevent the interaction of other characters and could, therefore, cause plot holes.

To conduct this test, *A Game of Thrones* will be used, the first book of the *A Song of Ice and Fire* novel series by George R. R. Martin. The work lends itself well to conducting this experiment for several reasons: the first is that it contains a large number of characters (187 to be precise), making the result statistically more significant than a book with fewer characters; the second reason is that death plays a fundamental role in this work: 45 characters die just on the first book, and 7 are already dead before the beginning of the story.

Datasets

The data is automatically obtained through an algorithm that takes the text of *A Game of Thrones* and the list of characters' names as input, and outputs a network where two nodes are connected if they have appeared at least once simultaneously within 15 words. Connection refers to both direct and indirect interaction. For example, interactions are the appearance of two characters in the same place, a conversation, or a character talking about another character. Additionally, their edge is weighted by how many times this condition occurs and any edges of weight one or two were automatically removed from the network, judging these connections to be incidental. The data was not created by the author of this experiment but was downloaded from the following GitHub repository, created by the Professor at the Macalester College Andrew Beveridge in 2017: <https://github.com/mathbeveridge/asoiaf>.

After downloading the data from the repository in csv format, it was converted to DL format to be better processed by Ucinet, the software that will be used to conduct this study. To obtain this result, the DL Editor was used, selecting as data format "Edgelist1 ego alter [value]", since the csv was precisely structured in three columns, in which the first was the individual (ego), the second the contact (alter) and the third the number of interactions. The outcome was an adjacency matrix with the elements A_{ij} equal to the weights of the corresponding connections. It is possible to observe that, being an undirected network, the values are symmetrical with respect to the diagonal and, as there are no self-loops, the diagonal is made up of only zeros. To reduce the memory occupied by the file and to make subsequent operations more efficient, symmetrical data was removed, keeping only those present in the triangle above the diagonal. The matrix for the first 25 characters in alphabetical order is given as an example (figure 1).

Figure 1: Weighted adjacency matrix of the relationships between the first 25 characters in alphabetical order.

In addition to the data on the relationships between the characters, in order to prepare a test that takes into account their status as dead or alive at the end of the book, it was also necessary to create a table

with this type of information. Also, for this purpose, Ucinet's DL Editor was used, but selecting "Matrix" as the data format, because it allows to specify the labels of the columns. The result is a table in which the first column contains the IDs of the characters in alphabetical order from 1 to 187, while the second contains 1 if the character is alive at the end of the first book, 0 if he is dead, empty if he was already dead before the beginning of the story or if his status remains unknown in the following four books. Once the centrality measures have been obtained, the nodes relative to empty cells will be expelled and not considered to test the hypothesis. The reason is that the purpose of the research is to find a statistically significant relationship between the centrality of a node and the probability of the relative character's death, and it would therefore make no sense to consider actors who were already dead or whose status remains unknown.

Validity and Reliability

As for the validity of the model created so far, or its adherence to reality, it is certainly not short of imperfections. For example, if two characters appear one at the end of a paragraph and the other at the beginning of the next paragraph, where the scene is completely different, this occurrence is considered as an interaction and added to the count. However, as it will be seen in the next chapter on measures, the resulting picture is qualitatively credible with respect to the plot.

Furthermore, it must be considered that even a manual process would not have been free from errors: it would have consisted in reading the text and reporting in a separate table the interactions of the different characters; a job not so different from the one of the copyists. Going back and forth from the apograph, that is the table, to the antigraph, that is the original text, *saut du même au même* could occur, which happens when the copyist involuntarily leaves out a part of the text isolated from two similar expressions and confusing to each other (Chiesa, 2002).

Therefore, the best compromise is to use both a manual and an automatic process, using the automatic one as a first approach and then verifying the results by hand, looking for each ego and checking if there is an interaction with the alter identified by the algorithm. However, it would be an enormous job that would go beyond the aims of this work and it is left to a possible future research.

Measures

Before being able to test the relationship between the centrality of the characters and the probability of their death, it is necessary to obtain the appropriate measures.

The first one applied was the degree, and in particular the weighted degree, which is more significant since we are dealing with a weighted network. It corresponds to the number of ties of a given type that a node has (Borgatti *et al.*, 2018). In this case, the weight of the ties is also considered, so, for example, since Eddard Stark has interacted with Petyr-Baelish 81 times, 81 is added to his degree and not 1.

In terms of an adjacency matrix A of an undirected network, degree centrality is the sum of the rows (or columns) of the adjacency matrix. If $\text{deg}(i)$ is the degree centrality of an actor i and x_{ij} is the input of the adjacency matrix, then:

$$\text{deg}(i) = \sum_{j=1}^n A_{ij}$$

It can be shown that if something is taking a random walk across the network, the probability of it hitting a particular node is proportional to its degree. While many important flows do not traverse the network as random walks, some, like gossip, do. This is the main reason why it was decided to

consider this measure for the study, as killing characters with a high degree potentially means killing a person in possession of information that no one else has. An example could be Petyr Baelish and Lord Varys, not surprisingly both among the top twenty characters in terms of degree.

However, degree has one major drawback, which is that it is quite rough. For example, not all ties have the same weight, since being connected to a person who is central to the network should be more important than being linked to a peripheral node.

For this reason, this work also verifies the eigenvector centrality, which still counts the number of nodes adjacent to a given node, but weighs each adjacent node based on its centrality (Bonacich, 1972). If x is the eigenvector centrality score and $1 / \lambda$ is a constant of proportionality called eigenvalue, the equation says that the eigenvector centrality x_t of a node t is proportional to the sum of the centralities of the nodes to which it is adjacent:

$$x_t = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{v \in G} a_{v,t} x_v$$

In this way, it is possible both to attribute greater centrality to those characters who have few interactions but with central nodes, and to resize characters that have many interactions but with peripheral nodes. For example, Gregor Clegane is the 42nd for degree, with 74 interactions, but the 28th for eigenvector centrality, as he often interacts with central characters, such as Robert Baratheon during the tournament to celebrate Eddard Stark's appointment as Hand of the King.

The eigenvector centrality works very well for undirected networks like this, since the typical problem of directed acyclic networks never occurs, whereby the eigenvector centrality of nodes pointed by others whose trail ends has in-degree zero is always zero.

Betweenness centrality is also relevant for this research. In fact, it measures how often a given node falls along the shortest path between two other nodes (Freeman 1979). From a mathematical point of view, it is calculated by computing, for each pair of nodes other than a focal node, what proportion of all the shortest paths from one to the other pass through the focal node. Finally, these proportions are summed across all pairs and the result is a single value for each node. The formula for a node i is given by:

$$x_i = \sum_{sd} \frac{n_{sd}^i}{g_{sd}}$$

where n_{sd}^i is the number of geodesic paths connecting s and d through i , while g_{sd} is the total number of geodesic paths from s to d .

The importance of this measure depends on the fact that it can be interpreted in terms of the flow control potential across a network, since having a high betweenness centrality means being in the position of intermediary between two nodes. If the other two nodes are unable to create ties independently from the node in the middle, that node represents the only possibility of communication. For example, both Daenerys and Drogo have a high betweenness centrality, as they represent the two hubs of the Dothraki community. They are in fact sixth with a value of 1484 and eighth with a value of 1115, respectively.

Finally, the last and most interesting value to be calculated is the local clustering coefficient. It is crucial because it is the one that comes closest to the hypothesis formulated. In fact, it represents, for a given node, the proportion between the node's connected pairs of neighbors and the total number of pairs. For this reason, it is used as an indicator of structural holes, i.e., pairs of nodes connected to a certain node but disconnected from each other. The node in the center, to a greater extent than what

was already seen for the previous measures, has the power to initiate or interrupt the communication between those two neighbors. Therefore, it is considered more unlikely that the author will decide to decree its removal from the network through death.

Once these measures are obtained, they will be used as independent variables in a logistic regression test, a type of statistical test that is used when the dependent variable is dichotomous, that is it can only take two values. It is therefore a monadic test level, which relates the characteristic of a node, in this case its centrality, with another characteristic of the node, that is whether the corresponding character is alive or dead at the end of the first book. The objective of the model is to establish the probability with which an observation can generate one or the other value of the dependent variable. However, logistic regression can only be used if some basic assumptions are satisfied, namely the appropriate outcome structure, the observation independence, the absence of multicollinearity, the linearity of independent variable and log odds and a large sample size (Schreiber-Gregory, 2018). Our dataset does not satisfy conditions two, three and five, because the observations are not independent of each other, the independent variables are linked to each other, and the dataset is not large enough. The permutation technique was used to solve this problem, i.e., the observed data was reassigned to the nodes in 10,000 different combinations. The Ucinet software then calculated to what extent these random configurations lead to the same result observed with the actual configuration. This proportion is called p-value and estimates the degree of confidence in rejecting the null hypothesis: if it is less than 5% it is possible to reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative one.

Results

This chapter will first analyze the results obtained by applying the measures of centrality illustrated and, subsequently, a logistic regression test will be applied in order to verify if any of them significantly influence the life and death status of the characters at the end of the book *A Game of Thrones*. The figure below shows the results obtained for the first ten classified of each measure.

Figure 2: First ten classified of each measure applied.

Although the relationship data was automatically extracted, the results are quite convincing when compared to the plot. Eddard Stark is the most central character in terms of degree, eigencentrality and betweenness, followed by Robert Baratheon. In fact, it can be said that all the events in Westeros are a direct or indirect consequence of Robert's request to Eddard to succeed Jon Arryn as Hand of the King. Conversely, Arya Stark, although she has many relationships with other characters as shown by her degree, is penalized in terms of centrality by having mainly contacts with peripheral nodes and not being taken into consideration for any decision. In fact, she loses positions both in terms of eigenvector centrality, placing 12th, and in terms of betweenness, where she collapses to 25th place. Therefore, the results obtained reflect her mischievous and independent behaviour.

More interesting is the local clustering coefficient, which brings out apparently secondary characters, but powerful, since they are in contact with people who do not communicate with each other. From this point of view, the most emerging nodes are those of Danwell Frey and Karyl Vance. Danwell Frey, in particular, is the only bridge between the head of the family, Walder Frey, Hosteen Frey and Jared Frey. These last three characters, in fact, in the first book never interact. Removing Danwell Frey's character would then mean making Hosteen and Jared isolated nodes. In fact, Danwell not only does not die in this first book, but he will not die in the next four. Similar is the fate of Karyl Vance, the only bridge between Clement Piper and the rest of the network. Perhaps it is because of this hidden importance that the character reaches the fifth book safely.

There is no need to dwell further on the results of the centrality measures, since the heart of the research is to verify whether one of these measures affects the life and death status of the characters at the end of the first book. The null hypothesis is that none of these measures statistically significantly affects the life or death condition of the characters at the end of the first book, while the alternative hypothesis is that there is a correlation between at least one of them and the outcome of the characters. After performing the regression test for each measure with a number of permutations equal to 10000, a p-value less than 0.05 was found for none of them. It can therefore be said that none of them have a statistically significant influence on the death of the characters and we must stick to the null hypothesis. The figure below shows the four results obtained.

Figure 3: Results of regression tests.

It is possible to interpret the result obtained through the author's personal poetics. In an interview with science fiction magazine "Galaxy's Edge", George R. R. Martin explained why he has chosen to kill off several of his main characters. "I think a writer, even a fantasy writer, has an obligation to tell the truth and the truth is, as we say in *Game of Thrones*, all men must die," he said. "All men must die" is in fact the literal translation of "Valar Morghulis", one of the most famous book's leitmotifs. "You can't write about war and violence without having death. If you want to be honest it should affect your main characters. We've all read this story a million times when a bunch of heroes set out on adventure and it's the hero and his best friend and his girlfriend and they go through amazing hair-raising adventures and none of them die. The only ones who die are extras. That's such a cheat. It doesn't happen that way. They go into battle and their best friend dies or they get horribly wounded. They lose their leg or death comes at them unexpectedly." He went on to speak about his philosophy on realistic writing. "Once you've accepted that you have to include death then you should be honest about death and indicate it can strike down anybody at any time," Martin said. "You don't get to live forever just because you are a cute kid or the hero's best friend or the hero. Sometimes the hero dies, at least in my books. I love all my characters so it's always hard to kill them but I know it has to be done. I tend to think I don't kill them. The other characters kill 'em. I shift off all blame from myself."

Therefore, it seems that the author has consciously decided to remove nodes regardless of their centrality and whether they are "the hero's best friend or the hero". The fate that best reflects this philosophy is certainly, in this first book, that of Ned Stark, who dies despite being, as we have seen,

the crucial character. In the same interview, George Martin compared him to another character in what he considers his main source of inspiration: Boromir in *The Lord of the Rings*. Not surprisingly, the two characters in their respective series are played by the same actor, Sean Bean. Just as Tolkien decided to permanently eliminate a key character like Boromir, Martin also wanted to close his first book with the death of Ned Stark.

Critique

Although the outcome of this research did not lead to the elaboration of a predictive model about the death of characters in literary works, it proved through mathematical models the authenticity of the poetics of George R. R. Martin, whose search for realism prompted him to the conscious removal of central nodes from the network of his work. The result obtained is therefore in line with what he stated, and it is believed that extending the research to subsequent books, or refining the interactions recorded by the algorithm through manual verification, thus improving the validity and reliability of the dataset, would not lead to significantly different results. Instead, it would be interesting to conduct the same study on other authors, such as Tolkien, who with the character of Gandalf clearly deviates from Martin's realism, killing the character in the fight with the Balrog and then bringing him back to life as Gandalf the White. Therefore, a provisional conclusion is that it is not possible to create a predictive model in this sense that applies to any literary work, but that each author has a different poetics and therefore a different model.

Bibliography

- Beveridge, A. (2017). *Character Interaction Networks for George R. R. Martin's A Song of Ice and Fire saga*. GitHub repository <<https://github.com/mathbeveridge/asoiat>>.
- Bonacich, P. (1972). *Factoring and weighting approaches to clique identification*. Journal of Mathematical Sociology, 2, pp. 113-120.
- Borgatti, S. P., Everett, M. G. and Freeman, L.C. 2002. Ucinet 6 for Windows: Software for Social Network Analysis. Harvard, MA: Analytic Technologies.
- Borgatti, S. P., Everett, M. G., & Johnson, J. C. (2018). *Analyzing social networks*. Sage.
- Chiesa, P. (2002). *Elementi di critica testuale*. Bologna: Pàtron, p. 67.
- Freeman, L. C. (1978). *Centrality in social networks conceptual clarification*. Social Networks, Volume 1, Issue 3, pp. 215-239.
- Hoover, D. L. (2013). *Quantitative Analysis and Literary Studies*. In Susan Schreibman and Ray Siemens (Eds.). *A Companion to Digital Literary Studies*. Oxford: Blackwell <<http://www.digitalhumanities.org/companionDLS/>>.
- Martin, G. R. R. (1996). *A Game of Thrones*. New York City: HarperCollins.
- McCluskey, M. (May 17, 2016). *George R.R. Martin Explains Why He Kills Off Your Favorite Game of Thrones Characters*. Time < <https://time.com/4338948/george-rr-martin-why-characters-die-game-of-thrones/> >.
- Newman, M. (2018). *Networks*. Oxford university press.
- Schreiber-Gregory, D. (2018). *Logistic and Linear Regression Assumptions: Violation Recognition and Control*. Henry M Jackson Foundation <https://www.lexjansen.com/wuss/2018/130_Final_Paper_PDF.pdf>.